

RMEO

REACTOR OPTIMISATION BY MEMBRANE ENHANCED OPERATION

**EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROJECT**

**REACTOR OPTIMISATION
BY MEMBRANE ENHANCED OPERATION**

REDUCING ENERGY CONSUMPTION

IN PROCESS INDUSTRY

CONTEXT

The immobilization of highly active and selective homogeneous catalysts by the supported ionic liquid phase (SILP) concept is extremely promising in the context of catalyst recycling and energy savings. By **merging the SILP technology with membrane reactor technology** for the first time, such homogeneous catalysts are applied for process intensification in an industrial setting.

INDUSTRY & ACADEMIA TEAMING UP AROUND A NEW CONCEPT OF "TWO-IN-ONE" MEMBRANE REACTORS TO REDUCE ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND EMISSIONS IN PROCESS INDUSTRY

ROME0'S AIM

The project gathers 9 European partners from industry and academia to **implement an efficient platform for the optimal design of new integrated reactors**. Applied to large volume industrial processes, the innovative ROME0 approach will:

- **improve selectivity and productivity** of industrial reactions, including raw material savings
- **reduce energy consumption** by up to 80% in industrial catalytic gas-phase reactions
- **reduce related emissions** by up to 90%

ROME0's "two-in-one" reactors combine optimized membrane modules and the immobilization of homogeneous catalysts to carry out chemical synthesis and downstream processing in a single step.

WHAT'S NEW WITH ROME0?

ROME0 intends to get detailed understanding of the processes involved in the well-argued design of new reactors, **from nano to macro-scale**. Two important reactions are chosen as demonstration cases:

1. **Hydroformylation**, to convert olefins and syngas to aldehydes (precursors for plasticizer alcohols).
2. **Water-gas shift reaction** which uses CO-containing syngas derived from biomass to generate hydrogen.

For both reactions, the project will show how to set up **adapted toolboxes** by optimizing choice via modelling and simulation. Based on the use of building blocks, it aims to facilitate the conception of apparatus for a large set of applications.

A NEW AND ESSENTIAL STEP TOWARDS THE CHEMICAL PLANT OF THE FUTURE: SAFER, WITH A REDUCED ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT AND HIGHER PRODUCT QUALITY

TWO-IN-ONE REACTOR
FLEXIBLE METHOD **CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS CATALYSIS**
BIO-ENERGY APPLICATIONS
PROCESS INTENSIFICATION
HYDROFORMYLATION **WATER-GAS SHIFT REACTION**
DEMONSTRATION PLANTS
REDUCED ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT
IMPROVED ENERGY EFFICIENCY
MEMBRANES **DOWNSTREAM PROCESSING**
WIDE INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS
OPTIMAL DESIGN

EUROPEAN PARTNERS

Evonik - Germany
Evonik Performance Materials GmbH // Evonik Technology & Infrastructure GmbH

FAU - Germany
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

RWTH - Germany
Rheinisch Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen

DTU - Denmark
Technical University of Denmark

BioEnergy2020+ GmbH - Austria

LiqTech - Denmark
LiqTech International A/S

EMH - Belgium
European Membrane House

CSIC - Spain
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ROME0 IN A NUTSHELL

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